

THE GENESIS OF TRAINING OF PEDAGOGUES IN THE HIGHER EDUCATION SYSTEM BASED ON FOREIGN EXPERIENCES

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Abstract. *In this article, the reforms implemented in the field of education and science, the improvement of the training of pedagogues in the education system, the reforms implemented in the field of education and science in foreign countries in recent years, the attraction of all kinds of social resources to education, the training of pedagogues in world practice, the specific characteristics of the educational systems of foreign countries, ways of development through means of pedagogical and psychological influence are highlighted.*

Keywords: *reform, education, continuing education, science, university, training, integration, idea, ideology, policy, thinking, vocational education.*

On the basis of the reforms implemented in the field of education and science in our country, the education of pedagogical staff on the basis of mutual social cooperation is gaining urgent importance. In the speech of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoev mentioning the issue of personnel in his address to the Oliy Majlis on January 24, 2020: “As we aim to turn Uzbekistan into a developed country, we can achieve this only through rapid reforms, science and innovation. For this, first of all, it is necessary to educate the new generation of personnel who will be proactive reformers, who think strategically, and who will be educated and qualified. That is why we started reforming all stages of education, from kindergarten to higher education. In order to increase the knowledge and level of not only young people, but also the members of our society as a whole, first of all, we need knowledge and high spirituality. Where there is no knowledge, there will be backwardness, ignorance and, of course, error. As the sages of the East say, “The greatest wealth is intelligence and knowledge, the greatest inheritance is good education, the greatest poverty is ignorance!” Therefore, for all of us, acquiring modern knowledge, becoming the owner of true enlightenment and high culture should become a continuous vital need”, the issue of mature and potential, educated personnel in the society remains relevant.

The reforms implemented in the field of education and science in foreign countries in recent years show the need to attract all kinds of social resources to education. Because quality education is the basis of socio-economic development. At the core of social reforms, the reforms carried out in the field of education at the current stage of development of society are of particular importance as they open up new opportunities for increasing the effectiveness of teacher and pedagogue training.

The analysis of the positive experiences introduced by the educational systems of the leading countries of the world has shown that the education and training process in higher educational institutions in the field of pedagogy, which prepare specialists in our republic today, should be organized at the highest level of requirements. As a result, the competitiveness of our

country's teachers in the global labor market will increase, academic and professional qualifications and skills will be sufficiently formed.

Our research is of urgent importance in the implementation of the priority tasks defined in the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan PD- No.6097 dated October 29, 2020 "On approval of the concept of development of science until 2030":

- improvement of the management system in the field of science;
- training of highly qualified scientific and engineering personnel and directing them to scientific activities;
- creation of modern infrastructure of science development;
- formation of a modern information environment that supports the development of science.

Analyzing the scientific research on the problems of improving the system of training pedagogues, in the world's leading scientific centers and higher education institutions, particularly, in scientific research institutes (Russian Federation, St. Petersburg), Service d'Information sur les Études et les Professions (France), University of Nottingham (Great Britain), University of Helsinki (Finland), Xi'an International University (XAIU) (Xi'an, China), McMaster University (Canada), Kazakhstan National Pedagogical University named after Abay (Kazakhstan) effective reforms are being implemented on pedagogical problems in the educational system, training of pedagogical personnel.

On increasing the effectiveness of training processes of modern pedagogic personnel with high culture, practical professional skills, innovative teaching methods and assessment criteria in education and training such pedagogue scientists as U. Begimkulov, N. Muslimov, O. Musurmonova, Yu. K. Babansky, M. M. Potashnik, V. A. Slastenin, L. S. Podimova, Kyvik S carried out scientific research works about the need-motivation sphere of the teacher, the dynamics of development, various issues of the activities of pedagogues under certain conditions.

In the doctoral dissertation of U.Sh. Begimkulov entitled "Theory and practice of organization and management of informatization of pedagogical educational processes" studied creating modern distance courses, N.A. Muslimov - theoretical and methodological bases of professional formation of vocational education teacher, O. Musurmonova - the issues of fundamental improvement of the training of pedagogic personnel in matters related to the pedagogical foundations of the development of the spiritual culture of students.

In their research works, Y.K. Babanskiy indicating theoretical issues related to the problems of professionalization of the systematic approach in pedagogy, M.M. Potashnik - clarification of the general methodological aspects of the teacher's readiness for pedagogical innovations, V.A. Slastenin and L.S. Podimova - the important feature of the pedagogue's work as a socio-pedagogical phenomenon in innovative activity, they explained the nature of the complex interrelationship between the general culture, creative potential and professional direction of the pedagogue.

Kyvik S. analyzed the issues of dividing the training of pedagogic personnel into a general and a special system in world practice. The scientist develops the general system of teacher training through the fields of socio-humanitarian sciences (philosophy, sociology, political science), foreign languages, and physical education. While in the US, more emphasis is placed on learning the basics of interpersonal relations, relationships, and communication, in Japan, all teachers need to have knowledge and skills in physical education and art science. In Israel, the Netherlands, and

Scandinavian countries, teachers' knowledge of foreign languages is supported. CIS, on the other hand, pays more attention to the ideological-political and ideological training of pedagogues, as well as to the development of the knowledge acquired in secondary general education schools according to the specialty of the future teacher. Even in foreign countries, the education system is implemented based on the educational standards of their own state and country and the procedures set by the government.

In the higher education system of the United States of America, great importance is attached to the individualization of education and the implementation of independent work of the student. In this process, professor-pedagogues play an important role as guides. The main goal is to develop the student's thinking, to teach him to think logically. Training of pedagogic personnel is carried out on the basis of a program designed for 4-5 years, followed by 4-6 months of pedagogical practice and strengthening of knowledge.

In Japan, universities accept students who have completed high school, middle school, or 12 years of regular school. There are about 500 universities and they are divided into categories. In the universities of the 1st category, there are 3 students for each teacher, and in the universities of the 2nd category - 20 students. In Japan, higher education is inextricably linked with vocational education. The higher education system includes the following types:

- a) full cycle universities (4 years);
- b) accelerated university cycle (2 years);
- c) vocational education colleges;
- g) technical institutes.

In foreign countries, the educational system and programs differ from each other in terms of psychological and pedagogical preparation. Such training usually starts from the first year in pedagogical higher education institutions, and from the third year in universities. In certain countries (for example, in France), the study of pedagogy, psychology and specific methods is carried out in special, specialized centers. In educational institutions of Germany and a number of other countries, the curricula of "General pedagogy", "Social pedagogy", "Comparative pedagogy" and similar courses are provided, but in the list of seminars, you can find not general, but subject (special) courses specific to a certain direction of pedagogy. Seminar topics reflect the range of scientific interests of professors and teachers, which causes the creation of a favorable scientific environment for engaging students in pedagogical and scientific research.

In the higher education system, the meeting of the above-mentioned problems with the pedagogical process naturally in the process of training Pedagogic personnel is one of the factors that hinder the effectiveness of the educational system of all countries. In the world practice related to the activities of universities, there is a tradition of solving problems through the educational process oriented to science, school and pedagogical activity. Education in Germany is conducted in two stages: *gruvt-schtudium* (basic preparatory stage) and *haupt-schtudium* (main stage). The stage of basic preparation lasts for the first four semesters, in which the basics of science are studied, special knowledge is almost not given. The main stage is directed to the formation of professional-pedagogical knowledge and practical specialization skills.

In conclusion, it should be noted that as a result of researches conducted in the field of education in foreign countries, improving the qualitative change of the education of the younger generation by teachers and pedagogues who have a proper understanding of the necessary professional qualities, necessary competencies and teaching processes;

study of international experience, traditions and educational trends, strategies, and introduce the system of application in the activities of higher education institutions of our republic;
reforming the country's education system by studying the education system of foreign countries;

development of the specific features of the education system of foreign countries based on the analysis of the areas of personnel training and social cooperation in the higher education system of our republic;

development of new programs for improving the professional training of teachers working in the education system of our republic;

implementation of integration in higher education are of great importance.

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